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Trmt9B functions in lineage commitment in the human embryo.

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We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Trmt9B as a lineage commitment factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

Citations

- 1.